

Driving Impact: Althena's Roadmap for AI Business Opportunities in CCAM

**Funded by
the European Union**

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
**State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI**

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This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research, and Innovation (SERI).

Trustworthy, explainable AI for safe and scalable automated mobility

Althena is a Horizon and SERI-funded research initiative developing trustworthy, explainable and human-centred AI solutions for Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM), with the aim of making AI-driven vehicle and transport systems safer, more transparent and easier for operators and regulators to adopt.

Artificial Intelligence is transforming how people and goods move. To unlock the societal and economic benefits of automated mobility we must combine high-performing AI with strong safeguards: transparency, privacy, ethics and accountability. Althena builds the methods, tools and demonstrators that make AI in CCAM both effective and trustworthy so operators, citizens and regulators can adopt it with confidence.

Althena has developed a portfolio of methods, tools and datasets to improve safety, robustness and transparency of AI in automated mobility. The project's exploitation plan maps these outputs into commercial and non-commercial pathways.

Key elements of the analysis performed during the project involved:

Figure 1: Key elements of the analysis

Context

Automation in road transport promises improved safety, lower costs and environmental gains, but real deployment faces barriers: public trust, regulatory complexity, technical robustness, interoperability and workforce shifts. Althena positions trustworthy and explainable AI as a core

enabler to bridge these gaps.

Needs

Trust and Explainability: practical methods, model and data cards, and governance checklists that make AI decisions auditable and understandable to regulators, operators and the public.

Robustness across edge cases: data and model approaches (synthetic/hybrid datasets, domain adaptation) to ensure perception and decision systems work reliably in diverse environments.

Standardised testing and KPIs: common XIL testbeds, benchmark datasets and KPI definitions to enable repeatable validation and certification workflows.

Clear IPR and exploitation pathways: transparent classification of foreground/background IP, licensing options and partner-level exploitation plans to unblock commercialisation.

Operational integration patterns: deployment-ready integration patterns, APIs and monitoring tools so fleet operators and OEMs can adopt AI modules with limited friction.

Regulatory alignment and policy support: guidance and policy inputs tailored to upcoming frameworks (e.g., EU AI Act) so pilots can be designed for compliance from day one.

Barriers

Regulatory uncertainty and certification load: evolving rules and unclear certification paths increase time-to-market and investment risk for high-risk AI components.

Technical maturity gaps (TRL mismatch): heterogeneity of TRLs across KERs, some modules near product readiness while others require further R&D and validation.

Integration complexity and interoperability: lack of standard APIs, heterogeneous stacks and diverse vehicle platforms make system integration costly and slow.

Data governance and privacy constraints: access to large, representative datasets is limited by GDPR and commercial sensitivities; anonymisation and provenance are non-trivial.

Market adoption risk / ROI proof: operators and OEMs require demonstrable ROI, safety gains and anchor customers before committing to wide roll-out.

Societal acceptance and workforce impacts: public trust, perceived job impacts and social acceptance remain barriers unless addressed through human-centred design and participatory engagement.

Opportunities

Open artifacts for ecosystem building: publishing model/data cards, benchmark datasets (e.g., MultiCorrupt) and open tools can catalyse research, attract adopters and position Althena as a standards contributor.

Demonstrations and pilots as trust builders: targeted demos (privacy-preserving on-board anonymisation, scene-understanding) and co-funded pilots with operators create tangible ROI proofs and accelerate uptake.

Standardisation and policy input: engaging with standards bodies and policy processes (AI Act preparedness) offers influence on future rules and creates first-mover advantages for compliant solutions.

Modular commercialisation routes: mix of open (datasets, methodology) and protected (software modules, integration services) exploitation routes allows partners to tailor business models (licensing, PaaS, consultancy).

Cross-sector partnerships and scaling: collaborating with infrastructure providers, edge computing vendors and operators enables scaling (digital twins, roadside units) and regional adaptation.

Sustainability and new business models: optimisation features (energy, routing, utilisation) open revenue streams and align with environmental/regulatory incentives.

Figure 2: Adoption Readiness Matrix

Market snapshot and trends

Automated and AI-enabled mobility is a rapidly expanding segment within the broader transportation market. Global forecasts point to robust growth in automotive AI and autonomous mobility-related revenues over the coming decade. Europe is an active region for CCAM (Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility) research, pilots and industrial activity; however, compared with the United States and China, large-scale commercial deployments (robotaxis, wide-scale driverless freight) remain limited and generally concentrated in targeted pilot zones and controlled operations. European actors are leveraging partnerships with global technology providers while focusing on safe, explainable and interoperable solutions to meet local regulatory and societal expectations.

Figure 3: Key European market characteristics

Figure 4: Market drivers and opportunities

Figure 5: EU-based AV technology providers

Overview of the EU regulatory context

The EU regulatory framework for AI and automated mobility is maturing rapidly and includes several complementary strands that directly affect CCAM technologies:

The EU AI Act:	The EU AI Act (entered into force on 1 August 2024) establishes a risk-based classification for AI systems and imposes special, strict obligations for “high-risk” systems. These obligations include robust risk-management and data-governance requirements, extensive technical documentation and record-keeping, transparency and user-information duties, human-oversight measures, and conformity-assessment. The Act also create an EU governance framework and market surveillance / enforcement mechanisms (including CE-marking and notified-body oversight for certain high-risk systems).
GDPR and data protection law:	The GDPR and related EU data-protection law remain the primary legal framework for personal data in CCAM. They require lawfulness, purpose limitation, data-minimisation, storage-limitation, integrity/confidentiality, and accountability, and place special restrictions on biometric and other “special-category” data (Article 9), which is often implicated by camera or sensor systems used for perception and identification. In practice, developers must apply privacy-by-design and carry out appropriate DPIAs; pseudonymisation/anonymisation and careful purpose scoping are key mitigations, but may not fully remove all legal obligations if identification remains possible.
Vehicle type-approval and safety regulations:	EU vehicle type-approval law has been updated to enable approval of advanced driver assistance and fully automated driving systems. Key measures include Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2022/2236 (amending Regulation (EU) 2018/858 to add technical requirements for small-series and driverless vehicles, and to address software update procedures) and Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2022/1426 (laying down uniform procedures and technical specifications for type-approval of Automated Driving Systems under the General Safety Regulation 2019/2144). These rules create an EU-level pathway for L3/L4 approvals (including small-series approval), but they are use-case and area limited (e.g. geofenced or defined routes) and require national implementation for routine, cross-border deployment.
CE marking and conformity assessment:	Under the AI Act, providers of high-risk AI systems must undergo the relevant conformity-assessment procedure before placing systems on the EU market, produce and retain comprehensive technical documentation, implement a quality management and risk-management system, and draw up an EU declaration of conformity. High-risk systems must carry a CE marking (physical or digital as appropriate) to indicate conformity with the AI Act, and Member States will designate notified bodies to conduct/oversee third-party assessments where required. Post-market monitoring and registration obligations also apply.

Figure 6: Regulatory Landscape for CCAM in the EU

While EU regulations set the overarching legal framework for CCAM, Member States currently differ significantly in how they implement those rules, in enforcement capacity, and in national road-traffic laws; differences that create practical obstacles for cross-border operations and the roll-out of pan-European services. The EU has introduced harmonised instruments (for example, the Implementing Regulation on type-approval of Automated Driving Systems (Reg. 2022/1426), the Data Act and the EU AI Act), but full practical harmonisation, notably of national traffic codes, operational authorisations, data-sharing arrangements and incident-reporting practices, is still incomplete and uneven across countries, which complicates routine cross-border services and limits large-scale deployments.

Ethical requirements, transparency, explainability and non-discrimination, map closely to legal duties for CCAM: explainability supports compliance and public trust but must be balanced with GDPR constraints (e.g. data-minimisation and purpose-limitation). Athena addresses these trade-offs through a combination of privacy-preserving engineering and governance: privacy-by-design for data flows; explainability-by-design (model & data cards, decision summaries and explainability maps); privacy techniques including on-board anonymisation, redaction/aggregation and synthetic data generation to reduce exposure of personal data.

Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

Exploitation strategy

Non-commercial: Open datasets, model and data cards, policy inputs and standardisation contributions to maximise scientific and societal impact.

Commercial: Licensing of software modules, industrial integration, joint ventures, productisation via partners' toolchains and pilots with operators/OEMs. Individual partner plans identify tailored IPR and business models.

Main Findings and Recommendations

Figure 7: Summary of findings

Figure 8: Recommendations for commercialization and exploitation

Roadmap for Exploitation of AI and Automation in the Road Transport Sector

Roadmap for Exploitation of AI and Automation in the Road Transport Sector

1 Consolidation and standardisation

Objective: Build foundational trust, validate the technology and prepare market entry by aligning with emerging regulatory frameworks.

COMMERCIAL

- Develop pilot projects in collaboration with vehicle OEMs, transport operators, and tech providers.
- Validate early business models for AI components (e.g. perception, data governance, safety systems).
- Identify and engage first movers in freight (e.g. last-mile logistics) and urban mobility (e.g. AV shuttles).

TECHNICAL

- Advance AI components from TRL 6-7 to TRL 8-9 via real-world demonstration.
- Finalise modular toolkits and interfaces for interoperability across platforms and fleets.
- Prepare connected infrastructure mapping for future deployment (e.g., V2X, 5G edge).

LEGAL AND REGULATORY

- Align with EU's AI Act, GDPR, and sectoral legislation.
- Develop guidelines for compliance and accountability in AI deployments.
- Establish dialogue with certification bodies to shape future assurance and liability frameworks.

SOCIETAL

- Launch public awareness campaigns around the role and limits of AI in transport.
- Involve vulnerable users (e.g., elderly, cyclists, people with disabilities) in design testing.
- Develop user-friendly materials to explain AI transparency and explainability.

2 Market entry and operational deployment

Objective: Transition from pilots to real-world deployment of technologies, tools and methodologies and consolidate commercial strategies with a strong focus on operator needs.

COMMERCIAL

- Begin scalable deployment of AI modules in logistics, bus systems, and ride-hailing platforms.
- Promote AI tools for dynamic routing, predictive maintenance, and operational analytics.
- Introduce Digital Twins and remote operation platforms for training and monitoring.

TECHNICAL

- Deploy multi-sensor fusion systems, runtime safety mechanisms, and explainable decision-making frameworks.
- Integrate AI into fleet and logistics platforms, supporting real-time, adaptive behaviour.
- Implement cross-domain pilots that combine freight, passenger, and infrastructure data.

LEGAL AND REGULATORY

- Conduct conformity assessments and audits for high-risk AI applications.
- Develop sector-specific standards and test protocols (especially for logistics and AVs).
- Advance legal frameworks on shared liability and human oversight in autonomous systems.

SOCIETAL

- Evaluate public perception and usability of AI-enabled systems through UX testing and surveys.
- Train operators and planners in human-in-command protocols and override mechanisms.
- Engage communities in co-design and localised adoption strategies, especially in rural or underserved regions.

3 Scale-up and ecosystem integration

Objective: Achieve systemic AI integration in road transport, supported by infrastructure, legal certainty and societal acceptance

COMMERCIAL

- Enable fleet-wide deployment in long-haul freight, urban public transport, and on-demand services.
- Create business models around Explainability-as-a-Service, automated reporting, and ecosystem data sharing.
- Establish AI marketplaces and licensing schemes for SMEs and solution providers.

TECHNICAL

- Integrate AI with connected infrastructure (C-ITS), cloud-edge systems, and multimodal platforms.
- Expand use of Digital Twins for operations, simulation, and emergency preparedness.
- Coordinate multi-vehicle AI systems (e.g. platooning, convoy management).

LEGAL AND REGULATORY

- Harmonise standards across borders with EU-wide certifications and alignment with UNECE/ISO norms.
- Embed AI assurance and auditing frameworks into transport certification procedures.
- Institutionalise ethics and oversight boards within transport authorities and fleet managers.

SOCIETAL

- Deliver AI literacy and upskilling programmes for transport professionals and operators.
- Foster citizen-facing transparency via public dashboards on AI performance and decision rationale.
- Embed social impact monitoring into large-scale transport automation projects.

